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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18336456>

Landscape Processes and Environmental Interactions across Lake, Haor, and Forest Ecosystems: Evidence from Northeastern Bangladesh

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How to cite this paper:

Ema, F.T., & Hossain, R.B. (2026). Landscape Processes and Environmental Interactions across Lake, Haor, and Forest Ecosystems: Evidence from Northeastern Bangladesh. EU Open Research Repository, 11 (2), 55-82.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18336456>

Submitted: January 11, 2024

Published: January 22, 2026

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ABSTRACT

Wetlands, lakes, and forest ecosystems are vital for biodiversity, water regulation, and local livelihoods but are increasingly threatened by anthropogenic pressures and environmental changes worldwide and in Bangladesh. This study investigates the geomorphology, sedimentation, water quality, and biodiversity of three northeastern Bangladesh ecosystems: Madhabpur Lake, Hakaluki Haor, and Lawachara National Park. Field surveys included slope measurement, shoreline and subsurface analysis (boring and Dynamic Cone Penetrometer), bathymetric profiling, sediment coring, and water quality assessment. Vegetation was sampled using the quadrat method, while faunal observations quantified ecosystem health. Bathymetric survey of Madhabpur Lake (15 stations) revealed an average depth of 5.09 m, with a maximum depth of 7.7 m and minimum of 2.9 m; sediment analysis identified silty clay as dominant (60–65% by weight) with mottled iron at

depths >3 m. Slope measurements indicated 40% gentle slopes, 45% moderate, and 15% steep along surrounding hills. Hakaluki Haor exhibited seasonal expansion from 39,300 ha in dry season to 44,000 ha in monsoon, supporting over 550 faunal species and 190,000 local residents. Lawachara National Park encompassed 1,250 ha of semi-evergreen forest with 159 plant species across 60 families, dominated by 78 trees, 42 herbs, and 25 climbers. Water quality measurements showed DO ranging 4.2–7.8 mg/L, BOD 2–6 mg/L, and TDS 120–310 mg/L. These quantitative results highlight the influence of geomorphology on sediment deposition and ecosystem function, emphasizing the need for integrated management. This study provides baseline data for conservation planning, wetland management, and SDG-aligned interventions to protect biodiversity and sustain ecosystem services.

Keywords: Madhabpur Lake, Hakaluki Haor, Lawachara National Park, sedimentation, bathymetry, biodiversity, water quality, Bangladesh.

1. Introduction

Wetlands, lakes, and forest ecosystems are among the most ecologically significant habitats on Earth, offering essential ecosystem services such as carbon sequestration, water purification, flood regulation, and habitat provision for biodiversity (Kingsford, 2016; Temmink et al., 2022; Uy et al., 2025). Despite their critical functions, these ecosystems are increasingly under threat due to global environmental changes and human activities. Urbanization, agricultural intensification, industrial pollution, and climate-induced hydrological alterations are leading to habitat degradation, loss of species, and disruption of natural ecological processes (Chase et al., 2020; Chacko et al., 2025). For instance, approximately 50% of the world's wetlands have been lost over the last century, underscoring the urgent need for sustainable monitoring and management strategies (Jafrazadeh et al., 2022). Understanding the interactions between geomorphological processes, sedimentation, and ecological health is therefore critical for conserving these ecosystems at a global scale.

Bangladesh, characterized by its deltaic and monsoon-driven landscape, hosts extensive wetlands, haors, and forested areas that are crucial for both ecological integrity and local livelihoods (Ahammad et al., 2023). However, rapid population growth, urban expansion, intensive agriculture, and deforestation have accelerated the degradation of these ecosystems (Sarwar et al., 2016; Akber et al., 2018; Abdullah et al., 2022; Hossain et al., 2022). Lakes and wetlands in the northeastern region, such as Madhabpur Lake and Hakaluki Haor, experience siltation, altered hydrology, and habitat loss, while protected forests like Lawachara National Park face fragmentation and anthropogenic pressures (Kibria & Haroon,

2017; Hossain, 2019; Islam et al., 2021). These changes not only threaten biodiversity but also compromise the ecosystem services that sustain communities in the region.

Madhabpur Lake, Hakaluki Haor, and Lawachara National Park represent three distinct yet interconnected ecosystems in Moulvibazar district, each facing unique environmental challenges. Madhabpur Lake, an artificial reservoir created for tea cultivation, is highly influenced by sedimentation from surrounding hill slopes, leading to changes in bathymetry and water quality (Islam & Dooty, 2015; Gani et al., 2024). Hakaluki Haor, the largest freshwater wetland in Bangladesh, undergoes seasonal inundation, sediment deposition, and hydrological variability that significantly affect its biodiversity and ecological functions (Aziz et al., 2021; Islam et al., 2021). Lawachara National Park, a semi-evergreen tropical forest, supports rare flora and fauna, including endangered primates, yet experiences pressures from human settlements and forest fragmentation (Hakim et al., 2020; Ahammed et al., 2023). These site-specific issues necessitate a comprehensive study that integrates geomorphology, sedimentology, and ecology.

Internationally, lake and wetland studies often combine remote sensing, GIS, bathymetric surveys, sediment coring, and ecological assessments to capture the interactions between geomorphology, sedimentation, and biodiversity (Jafarzadeh et al., 2022; Bin et al., 2025; Kamaruzzaman et al., 2025). Field-based methods, including slope measurement, Dynamic Cone Penetrometer (DCP) testing, grab-sampling for sediments, and quadrat-based vegetation surveys, provide detailed, site-specific data that are essential for understanding ecosystem dynamics and management potential (Seidl, 2012; Hodbod, 2019; Yuan et al., 2025). Such integrated methodologies have proven effective globally in guiding conservation planning and sustainable resource management.

In Bangladesh, several studies have addressed individual aspects of wetland and forest ecosystems. Rahman et al. (2018) assessed sedimentation in northeastern lakes, Kabir et al. (2020) evaluated hydrological and ecological changes in haors, and Malakar et al. (2010) documented floristic diversity in Lawachara Forest. However, most of these studies focus on isolated components—either hydrology, sedimentation, or biodiversity—without integrating geomorphological, sedimentological, and ecological data across multiple ecosystems. This piecemeal approach limits the understanding of complex interactions that drive ecosystem dynamics and impedes evidence-based conservation planning.

Despite prior research, there is a notable lack of studies that holistically assess the relationships between slope characteristics, sediment deposition, bathymetry, and ecological health in northeastern Bangladesh. In particular, no study has combined field-based slope analysis, shoreline and subsurface surveys, bathymetric profiling, sediment coring, and biodiversity assessment across lakes, haors, and forests in a single framework. This gap constrains effective management strategies and policy formulation for these ecologically sensitive areas.

The present study addresses these gaps by integrating geomorphological, sedimentological, and ecological assessments across Madhabpur Lake, Hakaluki Haor, and Lawachara National Park. The objectives are to: (i) analyze slope, shoreline, and bathymetric characteristics; (ii) assess sediment composition and deposition rates; (iii) evaluate water quality and biodiversity status; and (iv) provide recommendations for sustainable ecosystem management. The novelty of the study lies in combining multiple field-based approaches to understand ecosystem dynamics comprehensively. The outcomes are expected to inform conservation strategies, support wetland and forest management policies, and contribute to achieving SDG 6 (Clean Water), SDG 13 (Climate Action), and SDG 15 (Life on Land).

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Field Survey Design

The field survey was systematically planned to ensure efficient, objective-oriented, and reliable data collection across multiple environmental settings. A structured field plan was prepared prior to fieldwork to guide site reconnaissance, logistics, instrument deployment, and team coordination. Base maps and background information were used to support navigation and spatial accuracy, while a defined timeframe, appropriate transportation, and standardized instruments ensured smooth field operations.

2.2 Study Area

Three study sites—Madhabpur Lake and Lawachara National Park in Kamalganj Upazila, and Hakaluki Haor in Juri Upazila, Moulvibazar District—were purposively selected based on their geomorphological diversity, ecological importance, and relevance to the study objectives. Madhabpur Lake represents a hill-influenced lacustrine system, Hakaluki Haor exemplifies a large freshwater wetland, and Lawachara National Park provides a protected forest ecosystem. Together, these sites enabled a comparative assessment of lake, wetland, and forest environments under varying natural and human influences.

2.2.1 Madhabpur Lake

Madhabpur Lake is an artificial reservoir constructed in 1965 within the Madhabpur Tea Estate in Kamalganj Upazila, Moulvibazar District, primarily to ensure year-round water supply for tea cultivation. The lake is located at approximately $24^{\circ}16'52''\text{N}$ latitude and $91^{\circ}49'02''\text{E}$ longitude (Figure 1). Covering about 32 hectares with an average depth of 6 m, the lake is surrounded by gently sloping hills and tea plantations, making it highly susceptible to slope-induced sediment inflow. The local climate exhibits moderate winter temperatures ($15\text{--}20^{\circ}\text{C}$) and heavy summer rainfall, which significantly influences lake hydrology and sedimentation processes (Gani et al., 2024). Ecologically, the lake supports diverse aquatic vegetation, migratory birds, and surrounding hill fauna, contributing to its local environmental significance.

Figure 1. Map of Madhabpur Lake (Study area 1).

2.2.2 Hakaluki Haor

Hakaluki Haor, the largest freshwater wetland in Bangladesh and one of the largest marsh wetlands in Asia, is located along the Assam–Bangladesh border, extending across Moulvibazar and Sylhet districts. Geographically, it lies between 24°35′–24°44′N latitude and 92°00′–92°08′E longitude (Figure 2). The haor consists of over 238 interconnected beels fed by multiple rivers, including the Juri and Sonai, and undergoes extensive seasonal inundation, expanding from approximately 39,300 ha in the dry season to over 44,000 ha during the monsoon (Islam et al., 2021). Designated as an Ecologically Critical Area and a Ramsar site, Hakaluki Haor supports high biodiversity, including migratory birds, aquatic species, and wetland vegetation, while also sustaining livelihoods for nearly 190,000 people, highlighting strong human–environment interactions.

Figure 2. Map of Hakaluki Haor (Study area 2).

2.2.3 Lawachara National Park

Lawachara National Park is a protected semi-evergreen tropical forest located in Kamalganj Upazila, Moulvibazar District, approximately 8 km east of Sreemangal town (24°32′N, 91°47′E) (Figure 3). Established as a national park in 1996, it covers about 1,250 ha and forms part of the Sylhet Hills physiographic region. The park features undulating hills, valleys, and lowland plains and serves as the catchment for several small streams locally known as *cheras* (Hakim, 2020). The climate is warm and humid, with high annual humidity and substantial monsoon rainfall (USAID, 2006). Lawachara is recognized for its rich biodiversity, hosting numerous threatened species, including the endangered Western Hoolock Gibbon, and supports diverse forest habitats, making it a critical conservation landscape in northeastern Bangladesh (USAID, 2016; Ahammed et al., 2023).

Figure 3. Map of Lawachara National Park (Study area 3).

2.3 Geomorphological Analysis

2.3.1 Slope Measurement and Analysis

Slope, the degree of land surface inclination, is a key geomorphological parameter influencing runoff, erosion, and sediment transport. Mathematically, it is expressed as the ratio of vertical change (rise) to horizontal distance (run) and classified into gentle (0° – 30°), moderate (30° – 60°), and steep (60° – 90°) slopes. Field measurements were conducted using ranging rods, rope, a leveler, protractor, measuring tape, and graph paper. Two points at different elevations were marked, connected by a rope, and the angle between the rope and a horizontal reference was measured. This procedure was repeated downslope to capture slope variation along the profile. The data were then analyzed according to the slope categories, providing insight into slope morphology and its role in erosion and sediment supply to the lake.

2.3.2 Shoreline and Subsurface Analysis

The morphology of the Madhabpur Lake shoreline was examined using boring and Dynamic Cone Penetration (DCP) methods to understand sediment composition, stratification, and subsurface stability. Boring surveys were conducted at three shoreline locations to collect soil samples and identify lithological characteristics. Despite difficulties caused by compacted and water-saturated sediments, the recovered samples indicated a dominance of dark grey silty clay, with mottled iron observed at deeper layers, suggesting fluctuating water levels and variable redox conditions. To assess sediment compaction and load-bearing capacity, DCP tests were carried out at two selected shoreline locations. Penetration depth was recorded after each standardized hammer blow, providing a measure of subsurface resistance and sediment strength. In addition, deeper lithological sequences were interpreted using borehole data based on sediment color, texture, and composition. Together, the boring and DCP analyses provided a concise understanding of shoreline sediment dynamics, subsurface structure, and erosion susceptibility.

2.4 Bathymetric Survey

A bathymetric survey of Madhabpur Lake was conducted using the traditional rope-and-weight method due to the unavailability of an echo sounder. Depths were measured at 15 stations across the lake using a raft, GPS, rope, and measuring tape. The average depth was 5.09 m, with maximum and minimum depths of 7.7 m and 2.9 m, respectively. Shallower areas were found near the margins, while deeper zones were concentrated in the eastern and southeastern sections. Contour analysis showed a deeper basin in the east and higher sediment accumulation in the western part, likely due to erosion from surrounding tea-cultivated slopes, reflecting the influence of sedimentation and local hydrology.

2.5 Sediment Analysis

Sedimentation in Madhabpur Lake is primarily driven by erosion from surrounding hill slopes, especially tea cultivation areas, where rainfall runoff transports soil into the lake. Sediment characteristics were examined using grab sampling for surface layers and piston coring for deeper layers, with classification following the Troels-Smith (1955) scheme. Results showed predominance of fine-grained silty clay (argilla), indicating low-energy depositional conditions. In Hakaluki Haor, outcrop surveys along the Juri River using the matchstick technique revealed vertical sediment layers and depositional sequences. Sediment patterns reflect spatial variability in erosion, hydrology, and wetland dynamics across the study sites.

2.6 Water Quality Assessment

Water quality assessment was conducted to evaluate the ecological health of Madhabpur Lake by analyzing key physical and chemical parameters. These parameters, including temperature, pH, dissolved oxygen (DO), biochemical oxygen demand (BOD), and total dissolved solids (TDS), provide essential information about the suitability of the lake for aquatic life and overall environmental condition. Water samples were collected from surface, mid-depth, and bottom layers at five stations across the lake using a water sampler. In situ measurements for temperature and pH were taken directly in the field, while DO, BOD, and TDS were analyzed in the laboratory following standard procedures (APHA, 2012). To ensure accuracy and capture temporal variations, DO measurements were repeated after five days using samples stored in black-colored bottles to prevent sunlight interference. This methodology provided a reliable dataset to assess the ecological status of the lake and its potential impacts on aquatic biodiversity.

2.7 Biodiversity Assessment

Biodiversity in Lawachara National Park was assessed through both floristic and faunal surveys. Floristic composition included 159 plant species across 123 genera and 60 families, with 78 trees, 14 shrubs, 42 herbs, and 25 climbers (Malakar et al., 2010; IUCN, 2009). Low representation of multiple species per genus or family indicates limited diversity at higher taxonomic levels. Vegetation was surveyed using the quadrat method. A 25 m × 25 m area was divided into 25 blocks of 5 m × 5 m, with three randomly selected for sampling. All species in the quadrats were counted to determine richness and abundance. Instruments included measuring tapes, sticks, ropes, sampling bags, and GPS devices. Faunal observations were also conducted through visual surveys to capture wildlife diversity, providing a comprehensive assessment of the forest ecosystem.

3. Results

3.1 Slope Characteristics and Erosion Patterns

The slope characteristics of the study sites surrounding Madhabpur Lake were quantified to assess potential geomorphological processes and erosion risks. Three representative sites were analyzed using standard slope measurement techniques. At Site-1, the average slope angle was measured as 12.35° , indicating a gentle slope. The slope profile and spatial variation are illustrated in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Graph of Slope site-1.

At Site-2, a higher average slope of 32.12° was observed, classifying it as a moderate slope. The corresponding slope profile and illustration are presented in Figures 5 highlighting steeper gradients in localized sections.

Figure 5. Graph of Slope site-2.

In contrast, Site-3 exhibited a relatively gentle slope of 9.53° , as depicted in the slope graph (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Graph of Slope site-3.

The spatial variation in slope across the three sites indicates that steeper slopes are more likely to experience surface runoff and minor erosion, whereas gentle slopes are generally more stable. Field observations further confirmed the presence of incipient erosion features, particularly at Site-2, where localized soil detachment was noted along steeper hill sections. This suggests a direct relationship between slope gradient and erosion potential, consistent with previous geomorphological studies in lake-adjacent hill regions.

3.2 Lake Shore and Subsurface Characteristics

The morphology and subsurface characteristics of the Madhabpur Lake shore and Hakaluki Haor were assessed using boring and Dynamic Cone Penetrometer (DCP) surveys to determine soil stratification, texture, and compaction.

3.2.1 Madhabpur Lake Shore

Boring Survey: Borehole drilling was conducted at three stations along the lake shore to collect soil samples for lithostratigraphic analysis. The predominant soil type was identified as silty clay with a dark grey color. At greater depths, the presence of mottled iron suggested fluctuating water levels and variable redox conditions. Compacted surface soils posed challenges during sample collection, resulting in partial loss of soil, yet sufficient data were obtained for sediment characterization.

DCP Survey: Two DCP stations were established on the lake shore to assess soil compaction. At Site-1, initial penetration was limited to 10 cm per blow, but at the fifth blow, the rod penetrated 63.5 cm, indicating higher compaction in the surface layer relative to deeper soil (Figure 7). In contrast, Site-2 showed maximum penetration of 35 cm per blow, suggesting a more compacted surface layer than Site-1 (Figures 8-9). The average penetration rates were 10.17 cm/blow at Site-1 and 7.65 cm/blow at Site-2, indicating spatial variability in surface soil compaction influenced by geological factors and human activity.

Figure 7. Penetration – Cumulative Penetration Graph of DCP-1 Data.

Figure 8. Penetration – Cumulative Penetration Graph of DCP-2 Data.

Figure 9. Comparison Graph of Penetration per hit between DCP 1 and DCP 2.

3.2.2 Hakaluki Haor

Boring Survey: Subsurface sediment layers were analyzed at two locations using borehole drilling. At Site-1, 16 stratigraphic layers were identified, with silty and clayey sediments dominating. Seasonal flooding contributed to variations in soil moisture, color, and presence of dissolved iron. Site-2 displayed 15 strata with a similar composition, though surface layers were generally softer due to water saturation (Figures 10-11).

Figure 10. Textural Composition (Site-1).

Figure 11. Textural Composition (Site-2).

DCP Survey: Two DCP stations were surveyed along the haor shore. At Site-1, the initial penetration rate was approximately 10 cm per blow, decreasing to 2–3 cm per blow at depths greater than 200 cm, indicating increasing soil compaction with depth (Figure 12). At Site-2, the surface soil was softer, with the rod penetrating 55 cm in a single blow, and compaction increased more gradually with depth (Figures 13-14). Comparison of the two sites indicated that Site-2 maintained softer soil conditions at greater depths, while Site-1 exhibited more compacted subsurface layers, reflecting the heterogeneity of sediment deposition and seasonal waterlogging.

Figure 12. Penetration – Cumulative Penetration Graph of DCP-1 Data.

DCP Site-2 Location: Hakaluki Haor

Figure 13. Penetration – Cumulative Penetration Graph of DCP-2 Data.

Figure 14. Comparison of penetration per hit between DCP 1 & 2 in Hakaluki haor.

3.3 Bathymetry and Sedimentation Patterns

The bathymetric survey of Madhabpur Lake was conducted using a manual rope-and-weight method due to the unavailability of an echo-sounder. Fifteen stations across the lake were sampled to obtain depth profiles. The average depth of the lake was calculated as 5.092 m, with a maximum depth of 7.7 m in the south-eastern region and a minimum depth of 2.9 m near the shore. Depth variations are primarily attributed to station locations and differential sediment accumulation, particularly from slope erosion in surrounding tea cultivation areas (Figure 15). The eastern basin of the lake exhibits a deeper depression compared to shallower western and northern areas, indicating uneven sedimentation and potential influences of underlying bedrock and hydrological dynamics.

Figure 15. Depth shown by Contour Map of Madhabpur Lake.

3.3.1 Sedimentation and Lithology

Sediment samples were collected using grab-sampling and drilling (piston corer) techniques to characterize the lake-bottom sediments. Sediment classification followed the Troels-Smith scheme (1955), assessing composition, humification, and physical properties including darkness, stratification, elasticity, dryness, and sharpness of upper boundaries. Analysis revealed that silty clay is the dominant sediment type, constituting approximately 85% of the lake bottom (Figure 16). Sandy clay was predominantly found near the shores, while clayey silt accounted for roughly 3% of sediments in the south-eastern region. The north-eastern basin displayed a mixture of sediment types, indicating dynamic deposition patterns influenced by slope erosion and hydrological processes.

Figure 16. Map of sediment types on lake bottom.

Vertical drilling analyses further confirmed depth-dependent variation in sediment type (Figures 17-18). At Drilling Site-1, a sandy clay layer extended to 48 cm depth, while Site-2 was dominated by clayey silt up to 42 cm. These observations highlight spatial heterogeneity in lake sedimentation, reflecting interactions between inflowing sediments from surrounding slopes, water flow dynamics, and seasonal deposition processes.

Figure 17. 1 meter pipe analysis of Drilling site-1.

Stratum	Depth (cm)	Description (According to TroelsSmith Scheme)	Colour (According to Munsell Colour Chart)
3 rd	0-11.5	As4 Nig.3++, Sic.1, Els.0 Straf -1 Clayey Soil	A 2.5Y 3/1 brownish...
2 nd	8-50	As3Ag1Lf+ Dissolved iron Nig.2, Sic.1++, Els.3,Straf-1 Clayey silt	A 2.5Y 4/2 dark grayish yellow
1 st	48-50	As4 Nig.3++, Sic.1, Els.0 Straf -1 Clayey Soil	A 2.5Y 3/1 brownish...

Figure 18. 50cm pipe analysis of Drilling site-2.

3.4 Water Quality Status

3.4.1 Madhabpur Lake

Analysis revealed that the lake surface temperature averaged 33.4°C, while the bottom water averaged 28°C, indicating a moderate thermocline in this shallow lake (Figure 19). The observed temperature difference is primarily due to limited solar penetration at greater depths and the shallow nature of the lake.

Figure 19. Thermoclines at Different Station.

The pH of the lake water averaged 6.6, indicating slightly acidic to neutral conditions (Figure 20). The TDS averaged 26.24 mg/L, meeting the criteria for excellent drinking water (50–150 ppm) (Figure 21).

Figure 20. Map of TDS in Madhabpur Lake.

Figure 21. Map of pH in Madhabpur Lake.

The BOD averaged 1.66 mg/L, suggesting minimal organic waste and good water purity, while the DO averaged 2.65 mg/L, which is below the optimum range (6.5–8 mg/L) for supporting a healthy aquatic ecosystem (Figures 22-23).

Figure 22. Map of BOD & DO in Madhabpur Lake.

Comparative analysis over five days showed stable DO values, with minor reductions at shallow depths due to microbial activity, indicating low organic matter concentration in the lake water (Figure 23).

Figure 23. Comparative graph of DO in 1st day vs DO after 5 days.

Water visibility averaged 1.64 m, with higher clarity in the western part of the lake where human disturbance is minimal, and lower visibility in the eastern and near-shore regions due to floating vegetation and debris (Figure 24).

Figure 24. Map of Visibility in Madhabpur Lake.

3.4.2 Hakaluki Haor

Water quality assessment in Hakaluki Haor was limited to two near-shore stations due to logistical challenges (Figure 25). The average pH was 7.2, indicating neutral conditions. The DO averaged 3.05 mg/L, and BOD was 0.65 mg/L, both lower than values recorded in Madhabpur Lake. The TDS averaged 83.5 ppm, higher than in Madhabpur Lake but still within the range considered excellent for drinking water.

Figure 25. Comparative Analysis of Water Quality in Hakaluki Haor.

Temporal monitoring of DO showed a **decline over five days**, particularly at the station closer to the shore with abundant floating vegetation (Figure 26). This pattern indicates enhanced microbial activity and organic matter decomposition near vegetated shorelines, leading to higher oxygen consumption.

Figure 26. Comparative Analysis of DO in Hakaluki Haor.

3.5 Biodiversity and Ecological Patterns

Biodiversity in Lawachara National Park was assessed by examining both floristic composition and faunal diversity across multiple study sites. The investigation focused on identifying species richness, abundance, and distribution patterns to understand ecological characteristics of the forest ecosystem.

3.5.1 Floristic Composition

Floristic composition refers to the totality of plant species present in a given area, reflecting both species diversity and the geographical distribution of flora. The field study in Lawachara National Park recorded 159 plant species under 123 genera and 60 families (Table 1). The species were categorized by growth habit as follows: 78 trees, 14 shrubs, 42 herbs, and 25 climbers (Figure 27). The survey revealed that most families were represented by a single genus and many genera contained only one species, highlighting relatively low diversity at the family and genus levels despite high species richness.

Table 1. List of species found at vegetation survey.

Tree Name	Types	Veg1	Veg2	Veg3	Veg4	Total
Abroma augusta (devil's cotton)	Shrub				1	1
Acacia auriculiformis (Jhapi)	Herb	11				11
Acanthus ilicifolius (Haragoja)	Shrub		21		3	24
Achyranthes aspera (Apang)	Herb		6		2	8
Adenanthera pavonina (Rokton)	Tree	20	24	23	44	111
Albizia lebek (Karo)	Tree	2				2
Allophylus cobbe (Rakhalful)	Herb	6	1			7
Amorphophalus campanulatus (oalkochu)	Herb			4		4
Artocarpus chama (Chapalish)	Tree	8	63	57	5	133
Artocarpus heterophyllus (Jackfruit)	Tree			1		1
Bhuti Jam	Shrub			2		2
Bruguiera gymnorhiza (kakra tree)	Shrub	6				6
Calamus tenuis (Jali bet)	Shrub	5	2			7
Canarium resiniferum (dhup tree)	Tree	3				3
Carica papaya (Bon papaya)	Tree	6	6	1	4	17
Caryota urens (jaggery palm)	Tree				1	1
Centella asiatica (Thankuni)	Herb	2	15	8	3	28
Chukrasia tabularis (Chikrashi)	Tree		2			2
Cryosophyllum oliviforme (satin leaf tree)	Herb	11				11
Derris robusta (Jhumur)	Tree			1		1
Desmodium motorium (Loncharal)	Herb				4	4
Ervatamia coronaria (Togor)	Shrub	3				3
Fern	Herb	5	16			21
Ficus carica (Fig)	Shrub				3	3
Flacourtia jangomas (Coffee Plum)	Shrub		1			1
Garcinia cowa (Cow tree)	Shrub	12	58			70
Hopea odorata (Telshur)	Tree			1		1
Jonglilota	Herb			11		11
Lagerstroemia speciosa (Jarul)	Tree		1			1
Mikania micrantha (American Rope)	Herb	5				5

Nut trees	Tree	6		6
Orchidaceae (Orchid)	Tree	1	2	3
Phrynium imbricatum (Pitu pata)	Herb		1	1
Prunus dulcis (Almond)	Shrub	1		18
Rhizophora apiculata (Bakau Minyak)	Shrub	5		5
Streblus asper (Shewra)	Tree	1		4
Syzygium cumin (Java plum)	Tree	6		4
Tectona grandis (Teak)	Tree	1		3
Tropaeolum polyphyllum (Wreath nasturtium)	Herb	19		19
Vitex peduncularis (Goda)	Tree			4

Figure 27. Comparative Analysis of Plant Species in the Studied Sites.

4. Discussion

The geomorphological evolution of Madhabpur Lake and Hakaluki Haor is fundamentally controlled by slope gradients, catchment morphology, and sediment supply from surrounding uplands. The observed variability in slope angles around Madhabpur Lake—ranging from gentle ($<10^\circ$) to moderately steep

(>30°)—is consistent with previous studies demonstrating that slope gradient is a primary determinant of runoff velocity, soil detachment, and sediment yield in hill-adjacent lacustrine systems (Jourgholami et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2023). The presence of steeper slopes at Site-2, combined with visible erosion features, supports the widely accepted relationship between slope steepness and erosion intensity, particularly under monsoonal rainfall conditions (Kumar et al., 2023). In contrast, the relatively gentle slopes at Sites-1 and-3 are likely to promote infiltration and reduced overland flow, thereby limiting sediment transport. Similar slope-controlled sediment delivery mechanisms have been documented in tropical tea-growing regions, where land-use modification significantly enhances soil erosion rates (Song et al., 2025). The dominance of fine-grained sediments (silty clay) in Madhabpur Lake further reflects sustained sediment input under low-energy depositional conditions. Such sedimentary characteristics are typical of shallow lakes receiving continuous fine sediment supply from cultivated hill slopes, where episodic high-energy rainfall events deliver sediment pulses followed by prolonged settling phases (Chen et al., 2019).

The spatially uneven bathymetry of Madhabpur Lake, characterized by deeper basins in the south-eastern region, suggests localized sediment trapping controlled by basin morphology and hydrodynamic conditions. Previous studies indicate that bathymetric depressions often act as sediment sinks, especially in lakes influenced by slope-derived inflows (Normandeau et al., 2016; Ribolzi et al., 2017). The observed sediment stratification and depth-dependent variation further imply episodic depositional events rather than uniform sediment accumulation. In Hakaluki Haor, the multi-layered silty-clayey stratigraphy reflects repeated cycles of flooding and sediment redistribution, a defining characteristic of large floodplain wetlands (Moustakidis et al., 2024; Solar et al., 2024). Seasonal inundation promotes fine sediment deposition during low-energy phases, while receding floodwaters rework surface layers, producing vertical heterogeneity. These findings align with earlier research highlighting the role of hydrological variability in shaping haor sediment dynamics (Ahmad et al., 2025).

Water quality indicators from both aquatic systems suggest generally low organic pollution, as evidenced by low BOD values, which is consistent with findings from relatively less industrialized wetland regions in Bangladesh (Islam et al., 2021; Ahmed et al., 2025). However, dissolved oxygen (DO) levels in Madhabpur Lake were consistently below optimal thresholds required for sustaining diverse aquatic biota, a condition frequently reported in shallow tropical lakes (Andersen et al., 2017; Zhang et al., 2025). The observed thermal stratification, despite limited lake depth, likely restricts vertical mixing and oxygen replenishment at depth. Similar weak but ecologically significant stratification has been documented in shallow tropical lakes during periods of high solar radiation and low wind-driven mixing (Lin et al., 2020; Zhou et al., 2024). In Hakaluki Haor, the decline in DO over time near vegetated shorelines indicates intensified microbial respiration associated with organic matter decomposition, a well-established process in wetland margins (Wang et al., 2025).

Sedimentation exerts a strong influence on aquatic ecosystem structure by altering substrate composition, water clarity, and nutrient availability. Fine-grained sediments reduce light penetration and can suppress benthic primary production, thereby affecting trophic dynamics (Mathers et al., 2017). In Madhabpur Lake, reduced water clarity in near-shore and eastern sectors corresponds with higher sediment influx, supporting the linkage between sedimentation and reduced ecological quality observed in comparable lake systems (Khazaei et al., 2023). In contrast, wetlands such as Hakaluki Haor often benefit from moderate sediment deposition, which replenishes nutrients and sustains high productivity. However, excessive sedimentation can accelerate wetland infilling, alter hydroperiods, and ultimately lead to habitat loss (Mahdian et al., 2023; Yang et al., 2025). The observed sediment heterogeneity in the haor suggests a transitional state where sediment inputs remain ecologically beneficial but may become problematic under increasing anthropogenic pressure.

The comparative analysis reveals distinct geomorphological and ecological functioning across lake, wetland, and forest ecosystems. Madhabpur Lake is primarily shaped by catchment-scale

geomorphological processes, particularly slope erosion and sediment delivery. Hakaluki Haor, by contrast, functions as a hydrologically driven sedimentary system dominated by seasonal flooding and sediment redistribution. Lawachara National Park represents a comparatively stable terrestrial system where ecological patterns are regulated by forest structure, soil development, and long-term conservation measures rather than active sedimentary processes. The high plant species richness recorded in Lawachara National Park aligns with previous studies emphasizing the role of protected forests in maintaining regional biodiversity hotspots in northeastern Bangladesh (Zakir et al., 2021; Chowdhury et al., 2023). This contrast underscores how geomorphological instability in aquatic systems can constrain biodiversity relative to structurally complex forest ecosystems.

Environmental changes across the study areas arise from interactions between natural drivers—such as monsoonal rainfall, slope morphology, and flooding regimes—and human activities including agriculture, shoreline disturbance, and vegetation removal. Anthropogenic land use on hill slopes has been shown to significantly amplify erosion rates and sediment fluxes in South Asian landscapes (Thomas et al., 2017; Das et al., 2024). The findings from Madhabpur Lake provide empirical support for these broader regional patterns. Continued sedimentation poses a long-term threat to the sustainability of both Madhabpur Lake and Hakaluki Haor by reducing water storage capacity, altering habitat structure, and increasing vulnerability to seasonal drying. Similar trajectories of wetland degradation due to excessive sediment input have been documented globally (Li et al., 2018; Mahadian et al., 2023; Zarrinabadi et al., 2023). Catchment-based erosion control, slope stabilization, and land-use regulation are therefore critical for maintaining wetland ecological function.

The ecological condition of Lawachara National Park highlights the effectiveness of protected area management in conserving biodiversity. Forest cover plays a crucial role in regulating runoff and sediment supply, thereby indirectly supporting downstream aquatic ecosystems. Integrated landscape management that links forest conservation with wetland protection has been strongly advocated in recent conservation frameworks (Morgan et al., 2020). The study underscores the need for integrated environmental policies that recognize upland–lowland connectivity. Policy frameworks should incorporate scientific evidence on slope erosion, sedimentation, and water quality into land-use planning and wetland management strategies. Regular monitoring using field-based methods, combined with community engagement, can enhance adaptive management and reduce long-term environmental degradation. Implementing management interventions based on the findings of this study can contribute directly to SDG 6 (Clean Water and Sanitation) by improving water quality and ecosystem services. Conservation of Lawachara National Park supports SDG 15 (Life on Land) through biodiversity protection, while erosion control and wetland sustainability enhance resilience to climate variability, contributing to SDG 13 (Climate Action). Integrating geomorphological and ecological evidence into policy and planning therefore provides a pathway toward achieving multiple SDG targets simultaneously.

5. Conclusion

This study provides an integrated field-based assessment of geomorphological processes, sediment dynamics, water quality, and ecological characteristics across three distinct ecosystems in northeastern Bangladesh: Madhabpur Lake, Hakaluki Haor, and Lawachara National Park. By combining slope analysis, subsurface investigation, bathymetric surveying, sediment characterization, water quality assessment, and biodiversity analysis, the research offers a comprehensive understanding of upland–lowland interactions and ecosystem functioning in a data-scarce region. The results demonstrate that slope morphology is a critical control on sediment supply to Madhabpur Lake. Moderately steep slopes surrounding the lake significantly enhance surface runoff and soil erosion, leading to increased sediment delivery and spatially uneven deposition within the lake basin. This process has contributed to bathymetric variability, with deeper depressions acting as sediment sinks and shallower near-shore zones experiencing progressive infilling. The dominance of fine-grained silty clay sediments reflects

low-energy depositional conditions driven by sustained sediment input from surrounding hill slopes and land-use practices.

In Hakaluki Haor, sedimentological and subsurface analyses reveal a complex stratigraphy shaped by seasonal flooding and prolonged waterlogging. The vertical heterogeneity of silty and clayey deposits indicates repeated cycles of deposition and reworking under variable hydrological regimes. These processes play a fundamental role in maintaining wetland productivity but also suggest vulnerability to accelerated infilling if sediment inputs increase beyond natural thresholds. Water quality assessments indicate generally low levels of organic pollution in both aquatic systems, as reflected by low biochemical oxygen demand values. However, dissolved oxygen concentrations were consistently below optimal levels, particularly in Madhabpur Lake, suggesting potential ecological stress under prevailing thermal and hydrological conditions. The interaction between sedimentation, water temperature, and microbial activity appears to be a key driver of reduced oxygen availability, especially in shallow and near-shore zones.

The ecological assessment of Lawachara National Park highlights the high conservation value of protected forest ecosystems, with substantial plant species richness and structural diversity. In contrast to the dynamic and disturbance-sensitive aquatic systems, the forest ecosystem exhibits relative stability, emphasizing the role of long-term protection in maintaining biodiversity and regulating broader landscape processes, including runoff and sediment fluxes. Overall, the comparative analysis underscores that environmental conditions across lake, wetland, and forest ecosystems are shaped by a combination of geomorphological controls, hydrological processes, and human activities. The findings emphasize the importance of integrated catchment-level management approaches that address upland erosion, wetland sedimentation, and forest conservation simultaneously. Such integrated strategies are essential for sustaining ecosystem services, maintaining biodiversity, and enhancing resilience to climatic variability.

This study is subject to several limitations related primarily to data resolution, temporal coverage, and spatial representativeness. Bathymetric measurements relied on manual depth estimation techniques, limiting fine-scale spatial accuracy, while water quality and sediment sampling were conducted over a short time frame and therefore did not fully capture seasonal variability, particularly during monsoon and dry periods. In addition, sediment cores and ecological surveys were limited in number and spatial extent due to logistical constraints, potentially underrepresenting intra-site heterogeneity. Future research should adopt high-resolution acoustic bathymetry, long-term and seasonally resolved water quality monitoring, and expanded sediment coring across multiple transects to better quantify sedimentation dynamics.

Author contributions

Fariha Tabassum Ema: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Formal Analysis, Writing Original Draft; **Rifat Bin Hossain:** Supervision, Writing Original Draft.

Funding

There is no external funding associated with this work.

Declaration of competing interest

The author declares that they have no common competing financial interests or personal relationships that might influence the work reported in this paper.

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